

Minimally invasive vs open prostatectomy: comparing effectiveness and clinical outcomes

Prostatectomía mínimamente invasiva vs abierta: Comparación de la eficacia y los resultados clínicos

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Abstract

Surgical approaches for the treatment of prostate pathology, especially prostate cancer, remain the gold standard for its localized variants, given the substantial number of benefits provided in most areas. For decades, radical open prostatectomy has been the go-to in most scenarios, given its simplicity, yet high effectiveness in oncological and functional outcomes. However, new minimally invasive radical prostatectomy (MIRP) alternatives provide similar outcomes with lesser perioperative complications and better short-term outcomes. Optimization is a never-ending quest in health science, and evidence is needed to establish which of the alternatives provides the highest benefits for the patients, including the cost associated with the procedure. This review aims to compare the effectiveness, the positive clinical outcomes, and the rates of adverse clinical outcomes of open radical prostatectomy and MIRP.

Keywords: Radical open prostatectomy, minimally invasive radical prostatectomy, prostate cancer, prostate pathology, surgical outcomes.

Resumen

Los enfoques quirúrgicos para el tratamiento de la patología de la próstata, especialmente el cáncer de próstata, siguen siendo el estándar de oro para sus variantes localizadas, dada la cantidad sustancial de beneficios que brindan en la mayoría de las áreas. Durante décadas, la prostatectomía abierta radical ha sido la opción en la mayoría de los escenarios, dada su simplicidad, pero su alta efectividad en los resultados oncológicos y funcionales. Sin embargo, las nuevas alternativas de prostatectomía radical mínimamente invasiva (PRMI) brindan resultados similares con menos complicaciones perioperatorias y mejores resultados a corto plazo. La optimización es una búsqueda interminable en las ciencias de la salud, y se necesita evidencia para establecer cuál de las alternativas brinda los mayores beneficios para los pacientes, incluido el costo asociado con el procedimiento. Esta revisión tiene como objetivo comparar la efectividad, los resultados clínicos positivos y las tasas de resultados clínicos adversos de la prostatectomía radical abierta y la PRMI.

Palabras clave: prostatectomía radical abierta, prostatectomía radical mínimamente invasiva, cáncer de próstata, patología prostática, resultados quirúrgicos.

Prostate-related pathology represents a significant economic and quality of life (QoL) burden for male patients. Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a relatively frequent condition in adult males, affecting nearly 14% of the worldwide population, with minor variations in different regions¹. Moreover, the impact of BPH on patients' QoL has significantly risen in the past decades. A recent study reported that over 2.4 million years lived with disability were attributable to BPH in 2017 alone, which is three times more than those attributed to the following most prevalent severe urological condition, prostate cancer (PC)². This is the second most frequent malignancy after lung cancer in men worldwide, accounting for nearly 4% of all deaths attributable to cancer in men³. The incidence of PC has steadily risen in the last decades, probably due to the extended longevity of the population, making it a genuine public health concern⁴.

The most relevant aspect of PC and BPH management is early diagnosis, which makes both conditions highly controllable. As a result, prostate screening has a high level of evidence supporting its implementation in men between 40-50 years, depending on risk factors⁵. Regardless of the specific condition, a surgical approach may become an option at some point, with high effectiveness and tolerability⁶. In the case of PC, radical prostatectomy remains the gold standard for surgical management in localized PC (LPC). In contrast, its role in disseminated PC remains uncertain and needs further research⁷. However, surgical approaches have been diversified in the last years, introducing alternatives to open prostatectomy, like minimally invasive radical prostatectomy (MIRP) with or without robotic assistance⁸.

The use of MIRP has significantly increased over the past 20 years. Notably, robotic-assisted MIRP increased from 1% to 40% of all prostatectomies from 2001 to 2006⁹. Patients intuitively perceive the MIRP approach as less prompt to complications than conventional open prostatectomy. It has been reported that patients who underwent MIRP require fewer analgesics, shorter hospital stays, and present fewer complications, with the setback of being significantly more costly¹⁰. Optimization is a never-ending quest in health science, and evidence is needed to establish which of the alternatives provides the highest benefits for the patients, including the cost associated with the procedure. This review aims to compare the effectiveness, the positive clinical outcomes, and the rates of adverse clinical outcomes of open radical prostatectomy and MIRP.

Open prostatectomy vs minimally invasive prostatectomy: is the cost worth it?

Radical open prostatectomy (ROP) has been the gold standard of surgical management in prostate pathologies with a volume larger than 75 g in places with restricted access to newer technologies. Even in developed countries, ROP remains a significantly frequent procedure compared to other surgical approaches¹¹. Two surgical approaches have been described for ROP, suprapubic (SP) and retropubic (RP). Both procedures have been extensively reviewed, and their advantages and disadvantages have been established^{12,13}. Evidence has regularly shown that SP-ROP has a higher incidence of postoperative complications in most scenarios. On the other hand, high-volume prostates were associated with increased bleeding when using the RP-ROP. Overall, the RP-ROP showed better outcomes, higher peak urinary flow, and a trend of lower International Prostate Symptoms Score (IPSS) in patients that underwent surgery because of BPH¹⁴.

The role of ROP in PC is constantly evolving and adapting to new research findings. No surgical approach is recommended in men with low-grade low volume Gleason 6 PC since it provides nearly no benefits compared to surveillance programs in these patients. However, in men with intermediate to high-risk PC, ROP remains an important and valuable option¹⁵. Regarding its effectiveness, it has been established that patients that underwent ROP have outstanding oncologic outcomes after six years of the procedure. Predictive factors like biochemical recurrence-free survival, metastasis-free survival, and cancer-specific survival are well over 90% at six years. In conclusion, ROP confers effective six-year cancer control, increases the QoL of patients, decreases the IPSS, and significantly increases survivability. Moreover, these results did not significantly differ from those in minimally invasive approaches¹⁶.

However, as with any surgical procedure, there are general and specific risks. Although postoperative risks have decreased with the evolution of surgical techniques, some critical complications remain relevant. Observational studies have shown that perioperative mortality is under 0.1%. Moreover, stricture of the vesico-urethral anastomosis has an incidence between 2-9%. Likewise, incontinence and erectile dysfunction have been reported as complications; however, severe incontinence is rare, but as many as 30% of the patients report light incontinence¹⁷. Other studies have shown that perioperative bleeding remains a significant concern, requiring transfusion in up to 8% of the cases. Similarly, urinary tract infection is present in nearly 5% of all patients, but it is almost expected considering the nature of the procedure¹⁸.

Laparoscopic radical prostatectomy (LRP) was first introduced in the 1990s, aiming to reduce postoperative pain and morbidity, and to provide faster recovery¹⁹.

However, LRP resulted in a long-term learning curve for urologists, severely limiting LRP application²⁰. At the beginning of this century, robotic-assisted radical prostatectomy (RARP) was introduced, significantly reducing the technical challenges associated with LRP, and thus shortening the learning curve. As a result, RARP was widely adopted as a standard procedure for clinically localized PC, and both LRP and RARP were labeled as minimally invasive radical prostatectomy (MIRP) alternatives²¹. Nonetheless, at the time, it was yet to be defined whether these minimally invasive techniques were superior to the conventional ROP, since long-term studies were lacking, and most comparative reports had low-quality evidence, were underpopulated, or had some methodologic inconsistency⁸.

One of the advantages of a laparoscopic approach is its less invasive aspect compared with a significant surgical incision, like the Pfannenstiel incision. In general, laparoscopic approaches require less postoperative analgesics, resulting in better outcomes solely from drug deprivation²². However, this is primarily true for surgeries that involve the upper abdomen, which tend to be more painful due to the interaction of the upper abdomen with respiration. As a result, there is less room for improvement in postoperative pain regarding prostatectomy²³. Another advantage of a laparoscopic approach is the positive pressure created by the carbon dioxide pneumoperitoneum. Pneumoperitoneum reduces the pressure gradient between blood vessels and the operative field, resulting in less bleeding²⁴. A meta-analysis by Parsons and Bennet evaluated and compared the operative blood loss in ROP, LRP, and RARP. The MIRP alternatives generally provided significantly better outcomes regarding operative blood loss²⁵.

Since the indications for ROP, LRP and RARP are identical (localized disease stage cT2 or less), comparing outcomes is relatively simple²⁶. In the past decades, several studies have intended to clarify the advantages and disadvantages of minimally invasive procedures compared to ROP. For instance, Hu et al.²⁷ were among the first to objectively compare the effectiveness of ROP against MIRP, with and without robotic assistance. It was reported that utilization of MIRP increased from 9% to 43% between 2003 and 2007. As expected, patients subjected to MIRP were more likely to have a median income of at least US\$60,000. After adjustment for confounders, MIRP was associated with shorter length of stay, lower rates of blood transfusions (2.7% vs. 20.8%; $P < 0.001$), less postoperative respiratory complications, and lower incidence of anastomotic stricture. However, it was also reported that the MIRP group had a higher incidence of incontinence and erectile dysfunction²⁷.

Regarding oncological outcomes, initial reports stated that MIRP with robotic assistance had the lowest biochemical recurrence rate, while there were no significant differences between ROP and LRP. However, these studies were based on short-term follow-ups²⁸. Studies

with more extended surveillance have reported divergent results. Diaz et al.²⁹ performed a 10-year follow-up of RARP patients, and oncological outcomes were similar to the open approach. Similarly, the LAPPRO trial reported that RARP and ROP oncological outcomes were similar after six years, and only high-risk patients seemed to obtain some advantage from RARP. However, no significance was found¹⁶. Furthermore, a more recent study stated that after eight years, the RARP group had better oncological outcomes than the ROP group. Authors stated that RARP had an overall better short-term profile with a similar-to-better long-term profile³⁰.

A systematic review and meta-analysis compared the functional and oncological outcomes of LRP, RARP, and ROP. The MIRP alternatives were associated with significantly lower perioperative blood loss, lower need for transfusion, and shorter length of stay. There were no significant differences between LRP/RARP and ROP regarding oncological outcomes. Furthermore, urinary continence and erectile function at 12 months were similar between RARP and ROP³¹. Similarly, another systematic review found that the most relevant differences between LRP/RARP and ROP were the mean perioperative blood loss and transfusion rates. However, these authors found that RARP was associated with significantly better continence and potency urinary rates than LRP and ROP at 3, 6, and 12 months after surgery. As in the previous systematic review, no differences were found concerning oncological outcomes³².

On the other hand, RARP has been criticized because of the higher costs concerning equipment and consumables, and the need for greater surgical expertise. A significant amount of research has yielded mixed results regarding whether RARP is cost-effective compared to ROP after accounting for outcomes, readmission, and reoperation rates. For example, Labban et al.³³ recently reported that despite RARP's higher cost, it was associated with over US\$2,000 saved during the 10-year postoperative period, given its superiority concerning oncological and functional outcomes. However, it has been proven that the mere availability of the robotic alternative represents a bias, as it is provided to the patient as a superior alternative, thus further reinforcing its use regardless of available clinical data, which is controversial³⁴⁻³⁸.

Surgical approaches for PC remain the gold standard for its localized variants, given the substantial number of benefits provided in most areas. For decades, ROP has been the go-to in most scenarios, given its simplicity, yet high effectiveness in oncological and functional outcomes. However, new MIRP alternatives provide similar outcomes with lesser perioperative complications and better short-term outcomes. Nonetheless, LRP and RARP are significantly more expensive than ROP. The minimum prerequisites for MIRP alternatives represent an enormous cost for healthcare institutions, therefore making the implementation of these procedures controversial. In countries like the United States, RARP is already the dominant alternative for PC management. However, countries with limited financial resources still question if migration towards this expensive approach is economically optimal. While evidence shows that clinical outcomes of MIRP alternatives are fairly superior to those of the ROP, institutional financial outcomes are yet to be established to further incentivize the migration to this new surgical approach.

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